

INTERNET OF THINGS AS A TOOL FOR OPTIMIZING PROCESSES IN AGRICULTURE

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Abstracts. The article explores the potential applications of the Internet of Things in agriculture in Uzbekistan. Farmers' issues are explored, and examples of IoT application in monitoring soil conditions, managing the quality and quantity of water utilized, monitoring animal health, decreasing losses during food storage and transit, and enhancing agricultural worker safety are provided. The primary directions of IoT application are discussed, such as agricultural and crop monitoring and water resource management. The article describes research strategies for studying specialized literature and Internet sources, as well as analyzing scientific and methodological literature on the subject.

Keywords: Internet of Things, agriculture, monitoring systems, new technologies.

ИНТЕРНЕТ ВЕЩЕЙ КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ ОПТИМИЗАЦИИ ПРОЦЕССОВ В СЕЛЬСКОМ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕ

Аннотация. В статье исследуются потенциальные возможности применения Интернета вещей в сельском хозяйстве Узбекистана. Изучаются проблемы фермеров и приводятся примеры применения IoT для мониторинга состояния почвы, управления качеством и количеством используемой воды, мониторинга здоровья животных, снижения потерь при хранении и транспортировке продуктов питания и повышения безопасности сельскохозяйственных рабочих. Обсуждаются основные направления применения IoT, такие как мониторинг сельского хозяйства и посевов и управление водными ресурсами. В статье описаны исследовательские стратегии изучения специализированной литературы и интернет-источников, а также анализа научно-методической литературы по теме.

Ключевые слова: Интернет вещей, сельское хозяйство, системы мониторинга, новые технологии.

Introduction

In the modern world, the Internet of Things (IoT) is becoming more and more popular and is widely used in various areas of life, including industry, transport and healthcare. However, agriculture is still one of the sectors where the use of this technology is still little known and is used to a limited extent.

One of the reasons for this is the lack of access to modern technologies and limited funding for agricultural development. However, with the advent of new technologies such as IoT, there are new opportunities to improve productivity and efficiency in agriculture in Uzbekistan.

One of the main problems faced by farmers is the need to control the quality and quantity of water used. With the use of IoT in agriculture, it is possible to create monitoring systems that will allow you to control the level of water in reservoirs and determine the flow of water on specific plots of land. This will reduce water costs and increase yields [1].

Another example of the application of IoT in agriculture is the use of smart sensors to monitor soil conditions, which will allow farmers to optimize land cultivation, choose the most efficient fertilization methods and improve crop quality.

In addition, IoT can be used to monitor animal health, reduce losses during food storage and transportation, and improve the safety of agricultural workers.

In general, the use of IoT in agriculture in Uzbekistan can significantly increase the productivity and efficiency of farmers, improve food quality and reduce production costs. However, realizing this potential requires greater adoption of new technologies and increased awareness among farmers of the benefits of IoT in agriculture.

Research methods

As research methods for the declared topic, the study of special literature and Internet sources, analysis of scientific and methodological literature on the topic, analysis of the results of the implementation of official documents, as well as comparison, generalization and systematization of practical experience were carried out.

The main directions of the implementation of the Internet of Things

The introduction of the Internet of Things (IoT) in agriculture in Uzbekistan can lead to significant improvements in productivity and efficiency in this industry. IoT can help agricultural enterprises in the following areas [2]:

1. Crop and crop monitoring: IoT sensors can be used to monitor crops and crops, which will allow agricultural enterprises to get more accurate information about the status of crops and crops, as well as weather conditions.
2. Water management: IoT sensors can be used to monitor water levels in rivers, lakes and other bodies of water, as well as control irrigation and watering systems.
3. Livestock management: IoT sensors can be used to monitor animal health, nutrition and housing conditions, which will allow agricultural enterprises to increase productivity and product quality.
4. Transport management: IoT sensors can be used to monitor vehicles, allowing rural businesses to optimize delivery routes and reduce fuel costs.
5. Warehouse management: IoT sensors can be used to monitor warehouses, which will allow agricultural enterprises to improve inventory management and reduce storage costs.

However, the introduction of IoT in agriculture in Uzbekistan may face some obstacles, such as a lack of qualified specialists and insufficient infrastructure. Also, it is necessary to take into account the cultural and economic characteristics of the region [3].

In general, the introduction of IoT in agriculture in Uzbekistan can lead to a significant improvement in productivity and efficiency in this industry, but requires serious efforts and investments.

Internet of Things and Deep Learning

Many may not notice, but the IoT has a huge impact on our lifestyle. Smart cities, smart farming, interconnected vehicles, various innovative industries - all these solutions are connected in one way or another with IoT. But if we talk specifically about IoT in agriculture, then in this area the Internet of things will have an even greater impact on the way we live [4].

After all, using advanced solutions of the Internet of things, farmers will be able to decently reduce their costs and increase production. And this concerns not only the rational use of fertilizers

and monitoring the health of animals, but also the optimization of the movement of agricultural machines, as well as a significant improvement in precision farming technology.

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a network of devices that can communicate with each other without human intervention. These devices can range from household appliances to industrial equipment. However, in order for these devices to work together, they need to have the ability to process and analyze data.

Deep Learning is a subset of machine learning that uses neural networks to analyze and process data. Deep learning enables IoT devices to process large amounts of data and make decisions based on that data.

The combination of IoT and deep learning allows you to create devices that can analyze data in real time and make decisions based on this data. For example, Smart Farming can use temperature, humidity, and light data to automatically adjust the temperature and lighting in a production facility [5].

The concept of the Internet of Things (IoT) is gaining momentum in the world of agriculture, and many farms in Uzbekistan are using this state-of-the-art technology to monitor critical information about their crops and fields. By using remote sensors to monitor soil moisture, air temperature and soil quality, farmers can make more informed irrigation and yield decisions. In addition, by examining the influence of various genomic and microclimatic factors, farm biologists can solve the problem of optimizing the quality of their crops.

With this in mind, many tools and technologies have emerged to support IoT deployment in agriculture. GPS/GLONASS trackers, animal activity sensors, RFID cards, parallel navigation systems, precision farming systems, drones, smart weather stations, scales, IP cameras, smartphones and animal milking systems all play a role in optimizing the efficiency and productivity of agricultural farms .

The development of artificial intelligence has also led to great advances in smart agriculture. For example, farmers use artificial intelligence and machine learning to monitor the health of their crops, from detecting plant diseases to counting crops and predicting the weather. This sophisticated integration of AI technologies is helping creative farmers build more profitable, sustainable and efficient farms from the ground up [6].

Prospects for the implementation of IoT

There are already many successful projects for the implementation of IoT in agriculture in the world. For example, in the United States, sensors are ubiquitous to collect soil, weather and crop data, enabling farmers to make more informed decisions. China uses drones to monitor crops and determine yield levels.

In Uzbekistan, there are a number of guidance materials aimed at introducing IoT in agriculture. For example, in 2019, the program "Development of the Digital Economy and Society in Uzbekistan for 2019-2021" was adopted, in which one of the priority areas is the development of IoT in agriculture.

The introduction of IoT in agriculture in Uzbekistan can take place in the following stages:

- Installation of sensors to collect soil, weather and crop data.
- Analyze data and make informed decisions based on the information received.
- The use of unmanned aerial vehicles to monitor crops and determine the level of yield.

- Implementation of automatic irrigation and fertilization systems based on the received data.

Let's consider the most effective modern solutions in more detail.

Precision farming. Precision farming in agriculture should be considered as a system that makes the practice of working with the land as controlled and highly accurate as possible. And especially when it comes to growing crops and livestock. In these two areas, precision farming in agriculture is a key component of the Internet of things and all its various solutions [7]:

- various sensors;
- control and management systems;
- robotic technology;
- autonomous transport;
- automatic equipment, etc.

Moreover, already today such precision farming systems are used by numerous agricultural enterprises around the world. Among such IoT software and hardware solutions in the agricultural industry, soil moisture control sensors, automatic irrigation systems with automatic regulation of the intensity and speed of water supply, etc. are used. Such devices of the Internet of things in agriculture increase the profitability of arable land, allow you to get higher yields, and help save on water consumption. And soil moisture sensors contribute to high agronomic support in the season and allow you to optimize resource costs. These are the main advantages and features of precision farming using such high-tech solutions.

Drones in agriculture. IoT in agriculture involves the use of drones - unmanned aerial vehicles that make the most diverse branches of the industry more efficient. For example, they can be used to assess the condition of planted crops on a large field, and can also be used for:

- irrigation;
- monitoring;
- irrigation;
- taking soil samples;
- planting plants.

The main advantage of using drones as part of the implementation of IoT in agriculture lies in their wide capabilities, namely:

- visualization of the condition of plants in the fields, control of their condition;
- fast and accurate mapping;
- measuring the height of planted agricultural crops;
- high potential in terms of increasing the yield of fields;
- measurement of chlorophyll and nitrogen levels in wheat;
- drawing up drainage maps;
- automatic detection and counting of weeds; etc.

Drones can be deployed with smart planning and a well-thought-out data collection and processing strategy [8]. Moreover, all these actions can be performed in real time. Therefore, drones in IoT in agriculture are a big step towards a large-scale modernization of the entire agricultural sector.

The information that drones can collect and transmit makes it possible to understand how healthy the grown plants are, predict yields, even count the number of plants in the field. And all

this significantly increases the efficiency of precision farming, because the received data is transmitted in real time with minimal human intervention.

The drone is able to collect thermal, multispectral and visual data right in the process of flying over the field and lands itself in the place from which it took off.

Monitoring of cattle. To monitor livestock, farmers can also use various IoT solutions to obtain information about the location and health of their animals. This data will help prevent disease outbreaks (by isolating diseased animals from healthy ones) and detect and then treat livestock diseases at an early stage. This solution will help to minimize mortality among animals and reduce labor costs in determining the location of livestock.

Smart greenhouses. With the help of smart greenhouses, you can significantly increase the yield of certain varieties of fruits, vegetables and other crops. But classic greenhouses allow you to control the condition of plants exclusively with the help of manual mechanisms [9]. And the "smart greenhouse" system allows you to minimize any manual intervention in the process of plant development and helps organize intelligent automatic control of climate and other important parameters.

Managing a smart greenhouse comes down to a one-time setup and systematic monitoring of the condition of plants. The sensors used in such an IoT solution will provide information about:

- ambient temperature;
- level of illumination;
- air humidity;
- atmospheric pressure, etc.

Moreover, on the basis of this technology, it is possible to organize advanced control of a smart greenhouse: turn on / off the light, open / close windows, control temperature and humidity, remotely work with ventilation, etc. And all these actions can be performed via wireless data transmission via Wi-Fi, 3, 4 or 5G.

Conclusion

Using advanced solutions of the Internet of things, artificial intelligence and deep learning, farmers will be able to significantly reduce their costs and increase production.

The Internet of Things allows objects to communicate and share information. It is an extensive network of sensors that are connected to each other. They collect reliable data and transmit it directly from fields and farms.

The digital transformation of agriculture requires specialists with new knowledge, as well as new "smart" solutions to help them. It is important to interest and motivate both students of higher educational institutions and practical workers in the agricultural sector for a deep study of computer technologies.

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